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Sealing Material Testing Across the H₂ Value Chain: Ensuring Performance Under Real-World Conditions

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Abstract

The hydrogen economy presents a unique set of technical challenges for sealing materials, driven not only by hydrogen's specific properties but also by the diverse operating conditions and media encountered along the H₂ value chain. Ensuring the durability and reliability of seals in this environment is critical for safe and efficient hydrogen applications. Freudenberg Sealing Technologies (FST) is addressing these challenges by replicating application-relevant conditions in lab-scale material testing. Following this approach, we aim to assess and predict the long-term performance of our sealing solutions to enable extended service life and maximum durability in demanding H₂ applications. Our research highlights the importance of comprehensive testing methods to meet the stringent demands of the hydrogen economy.

Introduction

Scaling up the production capacities of electrochemical stacks, as well as components along the hydrogen value chain, e.g. compressors, pumps, valves, and storage applications require robust and reliable sealing products which are easily assembled and exhibit superior lifetime. Long lifetime and robust solutions are a prerequisite to achieve cost targets which are set along the H₂ Value chain.^[1]

Freudenberg Sealing Technologies (FST) provides material and design expertise which is backed by a long-standing expertise in product testing and simulation. Using material specific models in our simulation departments, we can optimize the sealing function under various installation conditions and provide guidance to our customers on how to optimize component geometries for sealing integration on an industrialized production and assembly scale.

Here we present an extract of our testing expertise of sealing materials for both anion exchange membrane- and alkaline electrolyzers (AEMEL and AEL), as well as ammonia storage and transportation.

1. Scientific Approach

Our material models are qualified for the applications in electrolyzers through a series of classical bulk and surface sensitive testing methods, including chemical analysis, physical measurements and mechanical testing. All is fed into our material database, from which the know-how can be transferred to simulation approaches facilitating accurate product design and optimization in finite element analysis.

Furthermore, we have developed various accelerated stress test (AST) procedures specifically for our sealing materials, which mimic media, temperature and pressure conditions as close as possible to the real application.

By increasing operating temperature or gas pressure the acceleration of aging can be assumed according to Arrhenius law and law of mass action. Throughout many different experiments we gather properties before and after such ASTs, so we can model lifetime of sealing products through above-mentioned correlation between reaction kinetics and physical properties.

Additionally, by investigating the fluids after immersion, we can quantify leachable from FST's products to keep the operating electrolytes as clean as possible and exclude harmful influence on the processes (especially electrocatalytic processes) we are sealing.

2. Experiments/Calculations/Simulations

As an excerpt of our material compatibility, as well as aging methodology, we present test results for Alkaline, and Ammonia compatibility of our sealing materials which specifically qualified best for corresponding AEL, and Ammonia storage applications, respectively.

Figure 1: a) Tensile strength of EPDM for AEL applications after different immersion times in 30 wt.% KOH at 95°C. b) compression stress relaxation of same EPDM for AEL at different temperatures for Arrhenius estimation.

Immersion testing techniques have been adapted from well-established standards in other fields of sealing industry to the requirements of specific H₂ and derivative applications. Figure 1 shows such an example of our EPDM for AEL applications. To validate materials for AEL application, e.g., standard rubber coupons (ISO 37, S2 dog bones)^[2] are immersed in pressure vessels filled with 30 wt.% KOH solution. Temperature and oxygen exposure are set to emulate the conditions under harsh anode conditions and mechanical measurements are performed on specimen after varying ageing intervals.

Additionally, compression stress relaxation of the AEL EPDM was measured at various times and temperatures in air, to establish a trend in sealing performance according to the Arrhenius approach. These measurements and the corresponding time extrapolation of the data suggests that 50% of the sealing force will remain after 14 years of storage at 80°C.

Similarly for ammonia applications, the autoclave is filled with liquid ammonia and rubber coupons are stored under relevant temperature and pressure conditions. Figure 2 shows another EPDM recipe which has so far proven most stable under these conditions.

Figure 2: Tensile strength of an EPDM for ammonia storage applications after different times in 45 °C NH₃ at 18 bar.

3. Results

FST provides sealing products along the entire H₂ value chain. Not only do we extensively test these materials for compatibility with the required process, but the data gathered is used for application specific lifetime estimation and digital design verification through FEA prior to

first prototypes. The materials presented here are our workhorses for Electrolyzer sealings which have been qualified by internal tests and produce positive feedback in field application, as they are tailormade to serve these challenging applications. Further qualifications over longer periods of time are ongoing or planned, especially for storage applications. Additionally, to standard application, design verification plans (DVP) regarding specific customer needs are designed in close collaboration with our customers.

References

- [1] IRENA, **2024**, A quality infrastructure roadmap for green hydrogen, ISBN: 978-92-9260-639-8
- [2] ISO 37:2024-05, [ISO 37 - 2024-05 - DIN Media](#) (May, 2025)

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